

Feature	Description
General community features	
Set community access	Ability to make the community accessible only to logged in visitors or all visitors
Flexible community structure	Ability for moderators to define the community structure by creating and arranging categories and category groups
Basic community functionality	Visitors can vote / like and respond to topics
Private messages	Ability for users to send a private message to another user or
Subscription / messaging / mailings	Ability to subscribe to a topic or category in order to receive updates on new replies
Live search	Increase the chance of finding the right content / answer by suggesting content when using the search functionality
Spam filter	
Basic spam detection	Ability to filter spam based on community sentiment/vocabulary
Advanced spam detection	Availability of self learning spam detection based on machine learning and natural language processing
Deployment model	
Deployment model	Platform is deployed in the cloud and provided as a service and automatically scales up on peak traffic
Data security	
Comply with key standards	ISO / EN / DIN
Regular audits	Company is audited yearly on the performance and reliability of the Information Security Management System by an external and objective IIOC member inspection firm
Questions and answers	
Create questions and answers	Users can create questions and answer these
Organize questions	Ability for a user to link a question to a category
Notification	Ability to receive email notifications on new questions or replies
FAQ creation	Ability to create FAQs based on popularity of a question
Discussion forum	(same as Q&A)
Registration and authentication	
Register and login	Ability to register and login from within the community application or using SSO
Moderation workflow / curation	
Flexible view of topics	The moderator tool has a default view that shows all topics and can select from this: all unanswered topics, all reported, all new etc
Content analysis	
Analyse posts and other content	Ability to report on sentiment analysis and content insights for the benefit of other departments like Marketing, Product Development, Customer Service, etc.
Reporting	Ability to provide stakeholders data reports based on tagged/annotated communitycontent
Reports and analytics	
Key stats and trends	Availability to display a visual analytics dashboard in the community management tool, with charts and trend lines, on key statistics and trends: topics, comments, views, users, activity
In-depth reporting	Detailed reporting, eg on answered / unanswered questions
Integrate with 3rd party reporting	Ability to integrate Google Analytics as an external analytics tool to get an end-to-end view of community impact
"Gamification"	
Create ranks and roles	Ability for a moderator to create/manage a rank / role through an administration console - without programming
Automatic ranking	Ability to automatically give a user a rank / role / badge based on community activity
Organic search optimization	
Ensure high ranking in Google	Highly effective community ranking and content recognition, interpretation and adaptation by Google. Integrate with Google Search Console / Google Webmaster Tools for optimal web crawling results and data analysis. Support Open Graph metadata for community pages to provide automated crawling context to Facebook, LinkedIn, Google and Microsoft
Optimize pages for search	Optimized header and page structure semantics within community templates for optimal page crawling and ranking results

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